

Towards Affective Analysis of Animals in Poetry

Haider, Thomas

thomas.haider@uni-passau.de
Universität Passau, Deutschland

Introduction

Across literary history, animals have been used as metaphors to express social hierarchies, critique institutions, evoke emotions, and frame the boundaries between nature and culture (Heise, 1999; Glotfelty, 1996; Garrard, 2004; Dürbeck & Stobbe, 2015; McHugh et al., 2021, Feuerstein, 2021; Ortiz-Robles, 2016; Rowland, 1973). Mullin (1999) argues that animals in cultural texts are not merely decorative but central to how societies imagine themselves and their others. Textual representations reveal how animals are perceived and also how humans conceptualize value, agency, and power. Moreover, poetic depictions of animals reflect social attitudes towards non-humans (Derrida, 2008; Lönngren, 2015; Roscher et al., 2021), which, for example, makes it more acceptable to slaughter livestock (cows, fish) than companion animals (dogs, horses).

To investigate animal representation in literature, we developed a multidimensional annotation schema covering *target sentiment*, *agency*, *power*, and *diegetic/semiotic function*, dimensions that are reasonably well researched for human-centric NLP and also motivated from environmental humanities research (Rønningstad et al., 2023; Saeidi et al., 2016; Antoniak et al., 2023; Mendelsohn et al., 2020; Borgards, 2012, Roscher et al., 2021). This poster focuses on LLM prediction accuracy on these tasks in German poetry, with a case study on sentiment and metaphorical meaning, in an ongoing project geared towards measuring how animal representations changed over time.

Extracting Animal Mentions from Poetry

We matched animal taxa in a large German poetry corpus (Haider, 2024) using string matching and heuristics, identifying ~25k animal mentions in ~65k poems (17th–20th century). Table 1 shows the most frequent animals. Circa 500 random mentions with up to 10 lines of context were manually annotated (more for sentiment/diegesis, fewer for agency/power).

Taxon	Frequency	Taxon	Frequency	Taxon	Frequency
Nachtigall	1036	Hund	822	Adler	776
Pferd	653	Esel	521	Vieh	493
Wurm	462	Lamm	406	Hahn	378
Fisch	339	Schlangen	338	Bienen	333
Raben	315	Schlange	314	Tauben	308
Fuchs	299	Löwen	293	Hirsch	291
Brut	286	Wolf	265	Löwe	264
Taube	263	Reh	251	Schwan	250
Drachen	249	Schmetterling	236	Schimmel	233
Grillen	224	Aar	211	Schafe	208
Ungeheuer	198	Schwalbe	195	Kukuk	186
Kuh	184	Schaf	175	Bär	173

Table 1: Most frequent animal taxa in German poetry corpus.

Sentiment

Target-based sentiment (attitude toward the animal) was manually annotated with fair agreement ($\kappa > 0.5$), then tested with four LLMs in zero-shot setting (on 300 samples). DeepSeekV3 and LLaMA3.3 outperformed others, offering a useful signal for large-scale prediction. Mistral7B tended to overpredict neutrals. There are a few cases that still need to be addressed in the guidelines (e.g., how to annotate compassion).

Metric / Class	Qwen3	Mistral7B	DeepSeekV3	LLaMA3.3
Macro F1	0.659	0.337	0.692	0.696
Negative F1	0.797	0.226	0.762	0.778
Neutral F1	0.415	0.444	0.573	0.573
Positive F1	0.767	0.340	0.742	0.736
Negative Precision	0.724	0.875	0.752	0.690
Neutral Precision	0.595	0.292	0.526	0.623
Positive Precision	0.737	0.735	0.814	0.812
Negative Recall	0.885	0.130	0.773	0.891
Neutral Recall	0.319	0.924	0.630	0.531
Positive Recall	0.798	0.221	0.681	0.672

Table 2: Comparison of Model Performance on Target Sentiment Task

Agency and Power

Agency classification (DeepSeekV3, zero shot, Table 3) covers four classes: agent, passive, neutral, instrument. The model performs well on “agent” but often misses it, overuses “neutral” and struggles most with “instrument” (war horses). Passive vs. instrument is challenging. The model favors clear agency roles and may need refined prompts, few-shot examples, or a change of method, e.g., connotation frames (Antoniak et al., 2023), or semantic role labeling (Ariyanto et al., 2024).

Label	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Passive	0.612	0.547	0.577	75
Neutral	0.416	0.638	0.503	58
Instrument	0.135	0.500	0.213	10
Agent	0.877	0.496	0.633	115
Accuracy			0.543	258
Macro avg	0.510	0.545	0.482	258
Weighted avg	0.667	0.543	0.572	258

Table 3: Classification Report (Agency) with DeepSeek

Power classification (DeepSeekV3, zero shot, Table 4) shows best results on “powerful” animals, though precision is moderate, suggesting overgeneralization. “Neutral” is often missed, “victim” (sacrificial lamb) is frequently confused with others. Performance on “weak” is lowest. The model overpredicts strong/victim roles and underdetects neutrality and weakness. Future annotation/prompting/models must better handle ambiguity and context sensitivity.

Label	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Support
Powerful	0.541	0.800	0.645	75
Neutral	0.729	0.417	0.531	103
Weak	0.438	0.250	0.318	28
Victim	0.396	0.679	0.500	28
Accuracy			0.551	234
Macro avg	0.526	0.537	0.499	234
Weighted avg	0.594	0.551	0.538	234

Table 4: Classification Report (Power)

Diegetic vs. Semiotic Animals

To better approach agency and power (also attitude), we distinguish *diegetic* and *semiotic* animal mentions (Borgards, 2012; Häussler et al., 2024). Diegetic animals act as literal animals (in the story), semiotic animals represent something else metaphorically (sly fox, powerful lion), represent a broader cultural symbol (sacrificial lamb), or build up a larger (didactic) allegory.

We evaluated DeepSeekV3 with different prompting strategies. Zero-shot prompts retrieved “diegetic” instances well, but performed poorly on figurative categories. Explanation-based and few-shot prompts improved recall on metaphorical animals. Still, “diegetic” is overpredicted, and “metaphor” is regularly misclassified. “Symbol” and “allegory” remain the hardest to detect. Overall, the model favors literal interpretation and struggles with figurative nuance. Likely, proper tuning is needed for these classes.

Setup	Accuracy	Macro F1	Diegetic R	Metaphor R	Symbol R	Allegory R
Zero-shot	41.8%	0.267	0.924	0.190	0.226	0.000
Explanation	50.1%	0.435	0.825	0.323	0.547	0.222
Explanation + 1-shot	54.6%	0.458	0.813	0.431	0.472	0.250
Few-shot (Final)	53.7%	0.441	0.743	0.468	0.434	0.222
Support	529		171	269	53	36

Table 5: Prompt optimization for diegetic/semiotic classification (DeepSeek-V3).

Case Study: Eagle and Worm

Figures 1 and 2 show sentiment over time for eagle (Adler, 776) and worm (Wurm, 462), as predicted by DeepSeekV3. The eagle is largely positive, though slightly less so in the 20th century. Attitudes toward worms are overwhelmingly negative. Both unsurprising, but worth unpacking (also period 1550-1600 is statistically insignificant).

Figure 1: Eagle Target Sentiment over time

Figure 2: Worm Target Sentiment over time

To explore why these animals are appraised in a certain way, we explore poem interpretation with DeepSeek. We prompt the LLM to interpret the meaning of the animal in context and then to derive keywords from its own interpretation. This needs to be properly evaluated of course, but our first sanity checks are promising. We then take the 5-6 keywords that were generated for a given text, and measure the association strength between the predicted sentiment and the interpretation keywords. We use pointwise mutual information, z-score (magnitudes of deviation from the mean across all categories), and a Fisher Exact Test to determine significance ($> 5\%$ p-value).

The results from the keyword analysis (Tables 6 and 7 below) provide insight into the cultural and affective framings of these two animals within historical poetry. The eagle emerges as positive symbol of strength, transcendence, and victory, aligning with its canonical role. Negative associations (destruction, predation) appear less often but may point to moments of social criticism. The worm, by contrast, is typically tied to decay, mortality, and corruption, yet occasionally evokes themes of intimacy, humility, and transformation.

Canonical meanings dominate, but rarer, non-canonical framings, the eagle as victim or worm as redemptive, likely highlight poetic inversions that challenge symbolic binaries.

Finally, Figure 3 shows a network of 10 animals based on their keywords. Lion and eagle are close ('strength'), wolf and dragon are similar ('predator'), nightingale and phoenix are both 'beautiful', dragon and worm share (negative) attributes.

Figure 3: Network analysis of 10 animals

Conclusion

This preliminary analysis demonstrates that computational approaches to literary texts can capture symbolic and affective nuances, although the presented classification results still have room for improvement.

Future work will show a more complete picture of all animals, further develop and evaluate our interpretive framework, and refine annotation of agency and power dimensions. Multilingual corpora (Plecháč et al. 2024) promise comparative insight.

Top 10 Keywords for Sentiment: NEGATIVE (Adler)

keyword	observed	expected	pmi	z_score	fisher_p	
0	vulnerability	21	3.18	2.7236	10.0219	0.0
1	destruction	10	1.48	2.7601	7.0247	0.0
4	retreat	7	1.02	2.7761	5.9188	7e-06
6	suffering	5	0.57	3.1386	5.8852	1.9e-05
7	predator	7	1.14	2.6241	5.509	2.1e-05
14	downfall	4	0.45	3.1386	5.2634	0.000165
10	disruption	5	0.68	2.8756	5.2353	0.000101
11	betrayal	5	0.68	2.8756	5.2353	0.000101
13	threat	6	1.02	2.5537	4.9287	0.00013
12	predatory	7	1.36	2.361	4.8352	0.000111

Top 10 Keywords for Sentiment: POSITIVE (Adler)

keyword	observed	expected	pmi	z_score	fisher_p	
2	strength	351	302.76	0.2133	2.8888	0.0
3	transcendence	160	130.4	0.2952	2.6376	0.0
5	vision	40	29.98	0.4162	1.838	9e-06
15	victory	37	28.48	0.3777	1.603	0.000229
23	divine	60	49.46	0.2787	1.5083	0.000891
24	elevation	63	52.46	0.2642	1.4655	0.001294
29	triumph	40	32.22	0.3118	1.3755	0.002296
31	protection	50	41.22	0.2787	1.3754	0.002468
30	enlightenment	28	21.73	0.3655	1.3482	0.00244
40	freedom	229	210.58	0.1209	1.3054	0.004615

Table 6: Top co-occurring sentiment keywords for the animal entity Adler (eagle), Top 10 for positive and negative.

Top Keywords for Sentiment: POSITIVE (Wurm)

Keyword	Observed	Expected	PMI	Z-Score	Fisher-p	
0	joy	5	0.29	4.1219	8.8033	1e-06
3	love	6	0.80	2.8995	5.8110	6.6e-05
12	arousal	2	0.11	4.1219	5.5642	0.003277
13	gentleness	2	0.11	4.1219	5.5642	0.003277
14	affection	2	0.11	4.1219	5.5642	0.003277
15	craftsmanship	2	0.11	4.1219	5.5642	0.003277
22	intimacy	2	0.17	3.5369	4.4057	0.009459
23	shame	2	0.17	3.5369	4.4057	0.009459
24	nurturing	2	0.17	3.5369	4.4057	0.009459
25	essential	2	0.17	3.5369	4.4057	0.009459

Top Keywords for Sentiment: NEGATIVE (Wurm)

Keyword	Observed	Expected	PMI	Z-Score	Fisher-p	
1	decay	154	136.66	0.1723	1.5348	4e-06
2	destruction	103	89.68	0.1997	1.4376	8e-06
5	corruption	72	62.35	0.2076	1.2407	0.000115
17	mortality	54	47.83	0.1750	0.9024	0.00761
27	transience	40	35.02	0.1918	0.8489	0.01196
31	suffering	47	41.85	0.1673	0.8039	0.018415
39	decomposition	30	26.48	0.1802	0.6889	0.046471

Table 7: Top co-occurring sentiment keywords for the animal entity Wurm (worm), Top 10 (significant) for positive and negative.

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